

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOTOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article describes the potential and prospects for the development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan. In particular, the prospects for the development of national tourism are considered, which can help improve the position of the tourism industry of Uzbekistan in the world market. Environmental education is important for the successful development of the tourism industry. Given the favorable climatic conditions and unique landscapes of Uzbekistan, there are certainly grounds for the development of eco-tourism. In particular, the development of the tourism industry is considered beneficial for the country, as it stimulates the economy through tourism, increases the state budget, protects natural resources, ensures social stability in the country, expands interethnic and cultural ties, and increases foreign exchange earnings.*

Keywords: *ecology, ecotourism, nature, environmental education, travel, cultural heritage, education.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье описаны потенциал и перспективы развития экотуризма в Узбекистане. В частности, рассмотрены перспективы развития национального туризма, которые могут способствовать улучшению положения туристической отрасли Узбекистана на мировом рынке. Экологическое образование важно для успешного развития туристической отрасли. Учитывая благоприятные климатические условия и уникальные ландшафты Узбекистана, безусловно, есть основания для развития экотуризма. В частности, развитие туристической отрасли считается выгодным для страны, поскольку оно стимулирует экономику за счет туризма, увеличивает государственный бюджет, защищает природные ресурсы, обеспечивает социальную стабильность в стране, расширяет межнациональные и культурные связи, увеличивает заработок и поток иностранной валюты.*

Ключевые слова: *экология, экотуризм, природа, экологическое образование, путешествия, культурное наследие, образование.*

Introduction. Ecotourism in Uzbekistan is a journey to a country where the sun shines almost all year round, to the territory of dry, hot summer, warm winter, soft honey autumn and spring with its bright colors. Nature has painted the landscapes of Uzbekistan in soft pastel tones, mainly yellow, copper, ochre, dark green and blue. With elegant strokes, she depicted on canvas arid deserts covered with golden sand, gray steppes, green valleys strewn with poppies blooming like red velvet carpets, swift mountain rivers and picturesque blue lakes. The mountains turned out to be the most picturesque: from low mountain ranges in the northern part to a powerful rocky ridge with steep cliffs in the south – they do not leave the traveler indifferent.

The peculiarities of ecotourism, according to scientists, is that it promotes and satisfies the desire to communicate with nature. In addition, it prevents a negative impact on the nature of culture, and also encourages tour operators to travel for the ecology of the country.

Ecotourism is tourism associated with visiting relatively undisturbed natural areas in order to get acquainted with the natural, cultural and ethnic features of the area, without violating the ecological integrity and creating economic conditions under which the protection of nature and natural resources is beneficial to the local population.

Other definitions of other organizations do not differ much from the above, so we will not give them here, but will focus on this definition in more detail.

A closer reading of this definition makes it clear that ecotourism is

1. A trip to the wild, where the main content of the trip is contact with wildlife, as well as with local customs and culture.

2. Compliance with the rules and laws of the visited territory. Minimization of negative impact on local nature and culture.

3. Providing the local population with economic incentives for nature conservation through their participation and income from tourism activities. Support for the local economy. In the realities of modern society, this is perhaps one of the most important points in the definition of ecotourism.

4. Active participation in all environmental activities.

5. Ensuring the safety and "ecological quality" of all trips, hikes and excursions.

6. Environmental education and enlightenment.

Ecotourism in Uzbekistan has recently been formed as a full-fledged and independent part of the overall tourism industry. As you know, earlier foreigners had to register for every night of their stay in Uzbekistan. Today, the registration rules remain in force, but it has become possible to register both as a campsite and as an individual traveler. However, it is still not recommended to stay in hotels or guest houses for more than three days unaccompanied by travel agents. There are many monuments and places in Uzbekistan where you can feel unity with nature.

For example, a trip to the Aral Sea coast is a unique experience. Traveling along the disappearing sea, you can enjoy the untouched natural beauty of the Ustyurt plateau.

There, surrounded by the starry sky and the endless desert, you understand how important it is to take care of the world in which we live. Far from civilization and communications, we walk along the salty land, which was the bottom of the sea 50 years ago, observe the greatness of the huge Ustyurt plateau and enjoy the beauty of Sudochie Lake.

Environmental education is a systematic approach to the acquisition of environmental knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure a responsible attitude to the environment. The definition of environmental education is usually associated with the first conference on the issue, held in Carson City (Nevada, USA) in 1970.

After the UN Conference on the Environment, held in Stockholm in 1972, UNESCO began to orient the world scientific and educational community to the development of environmental education and enlightenment.

The introduction of environmental education cannot be achieved only by informing students about global environmental problems. Therefore, it is necessary to create a comprehensive and unified system of environmental education, including both theoretical and practical aspects. Thus, it is possible to instill in students a culture of action, environmental values and a sense of responsibility for the preservation of the environment.

As M.Gaibullayeva notes in her article "The role of the development of environmental education in the Republic of Uzbekistan", the importance of environmental education and upbringing, which today have become a requirement of the current period. The purpose of environmental education, according to the author, is:

"The purpose of environmental education is to identify and protect ecosystem components; to study the stages of evolutionary theory; to discuss the existence and protection of animals in the ecosystem; to discuss environmental situations; to study and discuss the ecological features of

mountains, rivers and deserts; to study coral stones and humid areas; to study and discuss the human impact on the environment.

She also included the most specific topics, such as: issues of general ecology; problems of rational use of resources; socio—legal foundations for the use of air, land, water, flora and fauna, landscape protection; introduction of innovative ideas in the field of environmental policy of Uzbekistan, international cooperation in the field of ecology and environmental protection, strengthening environmental, socio-economic, political aspects.

Environmental education and training are currently one of the most important factors in preventing environmental problems.

As we know, today in Uzbekistan such competitions as “Best School for Environmental Protection” and “Best Environmental Student” are held. In addition, competitions “Experience of Ecology” and “Best Environmental Project” will be organized for university and technical school students, designed to stimulate the desire of young people to protect the environment.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his report at a video conference meeting with representatives of parliament, political parties, EDU on July 12, 2017, especially emphasized the need for serious attention to the most important issue - increasing the level of environmental culture of the population. He also noted that such issues cannot be resolved only through administrative means; this can be achieved through nurturing in the hearts of the younger generation a love for their native nature and a responsible attitude towards it. The head of state identified the task of forming in the minds of the younger generation a reverent attitude towards the incomparable nature inherent in our people, inherited from their ancestors and carried through centuries of national value.

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